

HOUSEHOLD EXPENSES AND ADOPTION OF COMMUNITY FOOD ASSISTANCE PROGRAM: CONSUMER'S PERSPECTIVE OF INDIRA CANTEEN

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Abstract

Food insecurity, often referred to as “hunger”, leads to health issues. Food insecurity challenge has witnessed global economies involve private firms and markets participations from public. Various states have explored mitigation of food insecurity through public-private partnership (PPP) model. The recent Covid-19 brought in numerous challenges not only to economies but globally many people faced problems of food availability, food expenses problems, and dietary issues due to food insecurity. Significant disruptions in availability, consumption had worsening effect on food insecurity specifically in urban cities and towns where forced lockdown was food accessibility problems. The urban population faced with loss of income during Covid-19 lockdown, faced the risk of increased food expenses, food insecurity leading to issues of well-being and health. This study covers the fundamental issues of SDG2-accessibility, affordability and utilization of food- tactfully addressed through a public-private partnership (PPP) model in Bengaluru City of Karnataka State, India-called Indira Canteen from consumer's perspective. Using quantitative survey data from 250 randomly selected households from three different municipal wards of a local urban metropolitan community in Bengaluru City of Karnataka State, India. The study investigates the consumer's value perception on the PPP Government Initiative. The findings revealed customers have found the new PPP initiative model as an enabler of household food insecurity especially in terms of household expenses. Furthermore, it highlights amongst other pertinent findings, menu changes could lead to discomfort associated disturbances in the consumer's household expenses.

Keywords: Food Insecurity, Food Expenses, Household Expenses, Indira Canteen, Public Private Partnership, SDG2.

1. INTRODUCTION

COVID-19, declared as a pandemic by the World Health Organisation in March 2020, became a public crisis world-over, which led to a social and economic crisis in the lives of citizens of the world. The Covid pandemic shed light on the structural vulnerabilities of food systems (Canfield, et al., 2021). Food Security is a system where people should have physical, social, and economic access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food that meets their food preferences and dietary needs in order to lead a healthy and active life at all times (FAO, 1996). Food security will be significantly impacted, albeit in an unpredictable manner, over the course of the next few decades as a result of a changing climate, an expanding global population, rising food prices, and environmental pressures. Public-private partnerships (PPP) model play an

important role since it makes provisions for a public good or service using combined competencies of multiple stakeholders. Previous research has shown that PPP models promote social and environmental goals in developing nations (Wang, Zang et al., 2021; Canfield, Anderson & McMichael, 2021; Danse, Klerkx et al, 2020; Jindal, Patel & Waller., 2017). By utilising PPP models, it is feasible to establish systems of practise that are both sustainable and resilient (Nchanji and Lutomia, 2021). In addition, by utilising PPP with both strategic and tactical planning in place, gains in global food security can be realised (Smyth et al., 2021). The urban dwellers, unlike agriculturists, are dependent on the local stores and market for all their food requirements. As their settlements are in cities & towns, they tend to depend more on the public and private sectors for employment-directly or indirectly in an around main cities. Vulnerability of the urban poor to food insecurities is immense (Grasham, Korzenevica, & Charles, 2019). Urban dwellers Majority of urban poor live close to the poverty line (Stamoulis & Zezza, 2010). Global economies have embarked upon targeted and untargeted policies to address food security issues. Primarily, developed countries aim their food security policies at a targeted population with staple food rationing programmes to remove food destitution. The Global Report on Food Crisis reports that an estimated 283 million people globally faced acute hunger at the end of the year due to the hunger pandemic, coronavirus pandemic, conflict & violence, in addition to increasing food and fuel prices in the year 2021(World Food Program, 2021). Food security is said to be in jeopardy with the ongoing Ukraine war that has engulfed Russia and its neighbouring countries. To combat poverty, most economies launch various meal schemes and measures to try to ensure that all people have year-round access to safe, nutritious, and sufficient food. Economies ensure that such schemes are inextricably linked to poverty eradication, as well as address undernutrition and combat poverty. Poverty level reduction strategies for different strata of society—short-term or long-term—are established through major policies by various governments (Winters et al., 2004). The relevant dimensions of food security given less attention are accessibility, utilization, and stability (Hatab, Cavinato & Lagerkvist, 2019).

Furthermore, the COVID-19 pandemic has further worsened the situation, challenging many governments and their allied departments to rethink their economic and food policies developed to improve food accessibility for the poor. People have migrated to urban cities in search of livelihood and job opportunities, as rural women and men are no longer able to make ends meet on their own land, as urbanisation and rural changes have spread. As the world continues to urbanize, the number of low-income urban dwellers continues to increase, resulting in people seeking to settle in informal settlements in urban cities having incomes that are usually low in relation to the cost of food and other needs of the urban population. In Asia, India and Pakistan are among the very few nations that have initiated cooked food meal programmes for adults that are targeted at unsegmented populations to tackle large pockets of poverty, food insecurity, and destitution problems. The British brought the rationing system to India with a new way of thinking about it as a public distribution system. It has been in place for more than 60 years and has helped the government fight poverty in a big way. It has been reported that 35.2% of the Indian population lives in urban slums (The World Bank, 2019). Over the years, the Indian government has initiated a number of initiatives to help minimise

hunger, all of which have good intentions. The local state governments play a significant role in mitigating food insecurity and hunger for its citizens. Various schemes involving transfers and subsidies have been initiated to address the problems.

Despite the considerable research on food security schemes and public distribution systems in India, the extent to which cooked food and meals are accessible through a governmental system is not, to our knowledge, readily available in the literature. The existing studies focus on the public distribution system of food grains (Bohtan, Mathiyazhagan & Vrat, 2020; George & McKay, 2019; Pradhan & Rao, 2018) and migrant labourers' usage (Bhagat, Reshmi et al., 2020). There have been a few publications on PPP model of Indira Canteen schemes, but in-depth studies addressing customers' trust, loyalty, and food nutrition of public food meal schemes, including demographic character studies, are rare. In this context, the aim of this article is to explore the impact of one such initiative of the Government of Karnataka called the Indira Canteen to shed light on its influence on food security and food expenses.

With this aim in mind, we began the study with a brief literature review of the India's & SDG2, global food security issues. Following our research questions, we take up the review of literature of the food security measures in the State of Karnataka briefing on the public distribution system—the Indira Canteen food scheme in Bangalore. This is followed up with study methods, analysis, and findings. Next, we talk about our findings by talking about what the literature says about them. We end with a limitation where we talk about the scope of future research

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 SDG2

The United Nations (UN) sustainable development goals (SDGs) address poverty, protect the earth, and ensure that global citizens enjoy health, wealth, peace, and welfare by 2020. Of the 17 SDGs, which cover all countries and sectors of society, SDG2 is called "Zero Hunger." The SDG2 targets biodiversity, productivity, and production together with climate change, hunger elimination, malnutrition elimination, and control of micronutrient deficiencies, including socioeconomic factors that impact farmers and markets (Lapo, 2019). SDG 2 stands out in this context as an inherently interdisciplinary goal that addresses the global food system (Blesh, Jones et al., 2019). Barilla (2007) states that an important indicator of the health of the food system of an economy is evident from the extent to which the food produced by the system contributes to human health and well-being through healthy diets.

2.2 SDG2 and Food System

The food system has in recent decades emerged as a single comprehensive interdisciplinary paradigm wherein food security, hunger, and nutrition are closely related to the agro-ecosystem (Yila & Sylla, 2020) along with environmental consequences. According to Vandermeer et al. (2018), the global food system has failed to achieve its goal of food security. A bounty of focused topics that address multi-faceted problems of food security, hunger, and nutrition are receiving attention from various international organisations and bodies, both in the government

and private sector. The availability of food and the accessibility of food are a part of the food crisis. Food equity essentially emphasises the fair and just inclusion of all citizens of a society in terms of accessibility and availability of food (Gingell, Murray et al, 2022). Even though the availability of food and how easy it is to get food are two different parts of the food crisis, it is also important to pay attention to how food is used and how stable its use is (FAO, 2008). In the research literature, the concept of food security has been narrowly defined, focusing on livestock (Hatab et al., 2019). The sub-target 2.1 of the SDG2 talks about food security reaching the needy and poor in vulnerable areas by 2030 (Mancino & Coleman-Jensen, 2019). Increased urbanisation effects on the socioeconomic landscape, causing issues of food security (Beer, Lin, and McGill, 2016). "Food Deserts" are created in urban areas where fresh food access is limited by reduced market proximity combined with financial constraints and inadequate transportation (Ploeg et al., 2009; Thomas, 2010).

2.3 India's and SDGs

The constitution of India explicitly provides in Article 21 the fundamental right to life. This "right" interpretation includes the right to food and basic necessities (Saxena, 2018). The government of India, through their public distribution system and targeted public distribution system, has been continuously addressing the food security in the country. The Government of India, through the enactment of the National Food Security Act (NFSA) in 2013, aims for adequate accessibility and availability of quality food at affordable prices to enable a vulnerable population to live a life of dignity. This was implemented in all the states and union territories of India. The mid-day-meal scheme, the world's largest school feeding programme to support nutritional support to primary education, tackles "classroom hunger" to lure underprivileged children to school (Singh, 2019). The GOI and the state governments at the local level devised such integrated schemes to target all segments of society—both young and old—to entitle them to receive nutritious food free of cost or at a subsidised cost, converting the food security programmes of the government as legal entitlements. Among the various criticisms the NFSA faces, it is silent on the nutritional aspects, especially as malnutrition is an unaddressed evil problem. The act's benefits are ineffective during wars, disasters, and other such natural, man-made, and biological calamities. To address the silence on nutrition, in 2020, the GOI distributed fortified rice through the public distribution system in six major cities of India to tackle anaemia and micro-nutrient deficiency in the country.

2.4 Food Security in Karnataka

The Government of Karnataka, a state of India located in the southern part of India, embarked on food security measures to meet the objective of the Food Security Act. The national food security bill, 27th amendment (2011), targets public distribution schemes of subsidised food grains under the public distribution system, the others being the Annapurna Scheme and Antyodaya Anna Yojana schemes for the public. The government of India, along with all the states, aims to achieve the SDG2 goals by the year 2020. In this context, the National Institution for Transforming India (NITI Aayog), an institution that serves as a Think-Tank of the Government and a replacement for the Planning Commission of India, oversees the implementation of schemes of the various Ministries, coordinating with States for the

achievement of the goals and targets enshrined in the SGD2. The Government of Karnataka, among the various steps launched to eliminate poverty and make Karnataka a hunger-free state, launched Namma Canteen (Indira Canteen) in 2017 under the public distribution system.

2.5 Bengaluru & Public Distribution System—Indira Canteen Food Scheme

Bangalore, officially called Bengaluru, is the capital of the Indian State of Karnataka and is located in the south-eastern region of the Deccan Plateau. Consequent to the rapid development, the city's landscape changed with the accelerated growth and productivity and gave rise to informal settlements, or slums. As per the Karnataka Slum Development Board survey, there are 2804 slum areas in the state, and in Bangalore City alone, the IT capital of India, there are 597 slum areas (Karnataka Slum Development Board, 2019). Of these, 387 slums are notified under the Karnataka Slum Area (Improvement and Clearance) Act 1973. These slums in Bengaluru account for more than 10% of the city's population. McGranahan et al. (2016) argue that by achieving urban inclusion, cities are more likely to achieve human rights, broad-based sustainable development, and can essentially transform themselves. Food outlets play a vital role in addressing the issues of food availability, prices, and preferences in the context of public health. In 2016, the Government of Karnataka announced the idea of Indira Canteen—a PPP modelled state government scheme offering free meals thrice a day for the urban poor, labourers, and migrant workers. Along with Cheftalk Food & Hospitality Service Pvt Ltd. and NGOs, a formal announcement during the Karnataka State Budget was initiated with a budget of Rs.100 crore with a plan to set up one canteen in each ward of Bruhat Bengaluru Mahanagar Palike (BBMP). This body was the authorised local administrative body to operate and maintain the Indira Canteen Network, with funds from the State Government Exchequer. The first canteen was inaugurated on August 16th, 2017 along with 100 other such canteens all over Bengaluru. Based on a hub-and-spoke model system, each Indira Canteen has a centralised kitchen for food service. The food preparation is tendered to private food and hospitality establishments, NGOs, and NGOs-Adamy Chethana, Rewards, and ChefTalk (Hans, 2022). Each Indira Canteen approximately received 400 to 600 plates of breakfast and lunch, with about 100 fewer at dinner time as discussed in "Take a look..." (2017). In addition to the 174 fixed physical outlets, there are 24 mobile canteens that are operating. The breakfast, lunch, and dinner prices at each outlet are Rs. 5, and Rs. 10 for lunch and dinner. The food supply chain has four centralised kitchens catering to a pocket of outlets. At each centralised kitchen, more than 900 kilogrammes of rice are cooked every half an hour, a thousand four hundred and forty idlies in twenty minutes, and 300 litres of sambaar in one hour. Each centralised kitchen supplies all Indira canteens attached to it. Additionally, the BBMP has contracted two caterers to operate an additional 27 centralised kitchens in Bengaluru.

3. METHODOLOGY

The primary objective of this study is to examine how the Indira Canteen usage, frequency of meal intake, food menu, and quality of food affect the lifestyle aspiration relative to the user's demographics and economic characteristics. This research is exploratory, involving primary data collection across the geographical areas covering three municipal wards of urban Bengaluru and answers the following research questions:

1. How much does the amount of food each user gets depend on their income, gender, and level of education?
2. How does Indira's Canteen deliver the "Zero Hunger" objective regarding the patron's household expenses?
3. How is having a food security card or not having a food security card related to how often people use the canteen?
4. What elements of the patron's usage of the Indira Canteen have a positive impact on his perception of the social good of the Indira Canteen?

3.1 Sampling

A quantitative study was conducted to analyse the most possible reasons why the general public use the public adult meal scheme Indira Canteen launched in Bengaluru City, in the State of Karnataka, India using a questionnaire. The population of Bengaluru, as per the 2011 Census, is 8,520,435—of which 4,433,855 are males and 4,086,580 are females, emerging today as the most populous state after the National Capital of India-Delhi within a total area of 2196 square kilometres (Census, 2011). Bengaluru, famously known the world all over as the "Silicon Valley of India", has its share of educational and research organisations, also housing a large Kannada film industry. Nearly three-fourths of the population is urban. As per the Karnataka Slum Development Board report of 2019-20, the total slums identified in Bengaluru were 421 slums with a population of 40.50 lakhs, accounting for 18.57% of Karnataka State's urban population. Of the 421 slums identified in Bengaluru, the total population was 582,999. The study was carried out from August 2020 through January 2021 in Bengaluru households with children. From among 198 wards of Bengaluru, the study drew samples from 3 inner city slums in Bangalore Central, in the busy commercial hub of Shivajinagar, a major urban area in Bengaluru, to examine the usage of Indira Canteen.

3.2 Development and Building Up of the Questionnaire

The first group of items on the questionnaire related to the infrastructure of the canteen. The authors developed the questions after visiting three canteens to confirm that the design and structure of all canteens were confirmed to the government orders. The questionnaire was designed using a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1(Strongly Disagree) to 5(Strongly Agree) and was structured into three study dimensions; the first was the personal data of the users (gender, age, education, source of income, marital status, dependents at home, occupation, and

cooking facility at home); the second was with respect to the food served at the canteen (menu, accompaniment, quality, quantity); the third was regarding the personal opinion of the canteen user on his own eating habits; pricing of canteen food; prices of similar food at nearby food joints; and health & benefits derived from the usage of the canteen (Table 1). In the personal opinion of the user, some of the questions do not have a scientific justification but were deliberately inserted to check whether the answers demonstrated any opinions that were contradictory and contrasting regarding the monetary and health benefits derived as a result of a thoughtful choice of usage. The research was a descriptive cross-sectional study of households with children, and it used a questionnaire-based survey to collect data. The survey was given to 300 households in three wards: ward number 93 (Vasanthnagar), ward number 92 (Shivajinagar), and ward number 90 (Ulsoor). There were 250 households that contributed with usable data. The method of sampling that was utilised in each ward is convenient sampling. The data was analysed using the SPSS statistical package version 23, developed by SPSS Inc. in Chicago, Illinois. To the best of our knowledge, we present real-life data on some of the most likely reasons that the general adult population uses a government-subsidized meal for the first time. In the cases where the respondent had trouble reading or was illiterate, the questionnaire was completed through an interview. Prior to completing the questionnaire, verbal consent was obtained from each respondent in order to ensure that the questionnaire could be completed.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

4.1 A Profile of the Respondents

The study was conducted in three wards in the central business district of Bengaluru, Karnataka—ward number 93 (Vasanthnagar), ward number 92 (Shivajinagar), and ward number 90 (Ulsoor). Of the 250 respondents, the males (145 numbers, 58%) were more than the females (104 numbers, 42%). The median age was 39 years in the age range of 36–45 years (interquartile ranges (IR). There were 114(46%) respondents in the age range of 18–25 years, 42(17%) in the age range of 26–35 years, and 37(15%) respondents in the age range of 36–45. The highest number of respondents (43.0, 108 in numbers) were undergraduate degree holders, followed by 21 % (52 in numbers) who were matriculated levels. The majority of the respondents (185 in number) (74%) were wage earners, with only 64(26%) being among the salaried group. Among the salaried respondents, a majority of 78.1% (195 in number) were earning less than Rs.30,000 per month as salary, while among the wage-earners, the majority of them (119 in number) were earning a meagre daily wage of between Rs.500 and Rs.800, with 115(46%) respondents reporting a daily wage of above Rs.1000 per day. A large portion of the respondents—147 in number (59%) were people who were away from their hometown but living in Bengaluru—while 96 of them (39%) were either separated, widowed or divorced, and only 7(3%) were married and staying with their spouse. Among the 250 respondents, 33 % (81 in numbers) had 6 or more children, while 31 % (77 in numbers) had 2 or less than 2 children among those married, while 94 percent (237 in numbers) reported siblings as dependent on them..

4.2 Reliability

The reliability of the questionnaire was determined by Cronbach's coefficient and the intra-class correlation coefficient (ICC). The interclass correlation coefficients for reliability (ICC) estimates and their 95% confidence intervals were calculated based on a 2-way mixed-effects model. The average ICC was .981, with a 95% confidence interval ranging from 0.977 to 0.984 ($F(249, 11205) = 52.212, p.001$). These coefficients are moderate to high, suggesting a fair amount of consistency among the variables of study. Furthermore, an exploratory factor analysis was employed to determine the construct validity of domains taken for the study, using principal component analysis for extraction with Kaiser Normalization as the rotation method. Bartlett's tests were significant ($2(1035) = 10851.94, p = 0.0001$, with $KMO = 0.971$, indicating sampling adequacy. Five factors were sufficient to explain the underlying structure of usage preference, explaining 70.14% of the explained variance. These five factors—named appropriately as: good clean environment, quality food, tasty food, healthy food, fibre and fruit—were considered subscales of usage for further analysis.

4.3 Findings and Results

- 1) Research Question 1- How much does the amount of food each user gets depend on their income, gender, and level of education?

The study looked at how the number of meals eaten at the Indira Canteen and the demographics of the people who responded (Based on the literature, it was hypothesised that young people would frequently consume more meals from the Indira canteen in comparison to older people. Secondly, males would frequently intake meals from the canteen, and thirdly, wage-earners frequented the Indira canteen more frequently than salaried people. As a result, we test the hypothesis that demographics influence Indira Canteen Facility (HA1) usage. A Chi-square test was administered to understand the relationship between the two variables using a cross-tabulation. The results found that age was statistically significant with frequent intake of meals in the Indira Canteen with a Chi-Square function. The lower the age of the person, the higher the frequency of meal-intake from the facility. The age range of 18–25 had the highest number of meals per day (4 times) of 46%, while the age range of 56 and above was only 4%. In the category of 3 meals a day, the age range of 18–25 constituted 9%, while 56 and above constituted only 2% of the total sample. Chi-square and t-test analyses are used to compare the participant's characteristics with the frequency of meal intake at the facility. The chi-square test confirmed that gender was statistically significant with the intake of meals; 39% of the males frequented the canteen while only 16% were females. The number of people in the non-salaried group is 185. An independent t-test for mean difference for salaried and non-salaried showed a statistically significant ($p < 0$) variance difference between the two groups, indicating that the non-salaried people had more meals in the Indira Canteen ($M = 3.09, SD = 1.155$) than the salaried people ($M = 2.75, SD = 1.392, (t_{96.722} = -1.757, p .00)$).

A chi-square helped to understand the association between the demographics and usage but it will be more insightful to know how these variables together impact the user's household expenses. So we move on to the next research questions.

- 2) Research question #2: How does Indira’s Canteen deliver the "Zero Hunger" objective regarding the patron’s household expenses?

A logistic regression analysis test was performed to test the relationships between the independent variables - nutritious food, food accompaniment, price factor, price factor of similar foods in nearby food joints, the quantity of food served, and the discomfort felt in cooking and the dependent variable considered is the positive impact of usage of the Indira canteen on the household expenses. The survey on usage asked the question, "Has the Indira canteen had a positive impact on household expenses?" This question is a binary logistic equation in which maximum likelihood techniques of estimation are applied since OLS yields bias estimates due to the categorical nature of the target variable- impact of "household expenses". The dependent variable was converted for statistical purposes into a dichotomous variable “Yes” and “No”. However as there were many influencing factors leading to positive impact of the usage, a multiple logistic regression model is selected in this research. Thus the binary multiple logistics regression model in simplest form is stated as follows with $y_1, y_2, y_3 \dots y_k$ as the co-efficient of the influencing factors.

$$\text{Positive impact} = y + y_0 \text{ nutritious food} + y_1 \text{ food accompaniment} + y_2 \text{ price factor} + y_3 \text{ price of similar food in nearby joints} + y_4 \text{ quantity of food served} + y_5 \text{ discomfort in cooking at home.} \quad ()$$

The study estimates the probability effect of the vector of the food in Indira Canteen on the impact of its usage on the household expense in a typical Bengaluru household. The independent variable was tested for multi-collinearity using the collinearity diagnostics function in SPSS with a tolerance lower than 0.2 – the threshold level of tolerance. The empirical results showed that the logistic model was statistically significant (Chi-square =69.446, df =7, p 0.0001) (ref Table 1). The Hosmer-Lemeshow test indicated the model was a good fit to the data (p-value>0.524) (ref Table 2). The findings suggest that the independent variables taken together are significantly associated with the positive or non-positive impact of household expenses on the usage of the Indira Canteen.

Table 1 –Logistic Model Significance.Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients				
		Chi-square	df	Sig.
Step 1	Step	69.446	7	0
	Block	69.446	7	0
	Model	69.446	7	0

Source: Primary Data

Table 2: Showing Model Summary

Model Summary			
Step	-2 Log likelihood	Cox & Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R Square
1	84.124a	0.243	0.528
a. Estimation terminated at iteration number 8 because parameter estimates changed by less than .001.			

Source: Primary Data.

The variances of the independent variable, as indicated by Nagelkerke R-square, indicated that with the independent variables taken together, the model explained 53% of the variances in the dependent variable and correctly classified 95.2 % of cases (ref Table 3).

Table 3: Showing the Classification

Classification Table					
Step 1	Observed		Predicted		
			household expense		Percentage Correct
			NO	YES	
	household expense	NO	14	9	60.9
		YES	3	224	98.7
	Overall Percentage				95.2
a. The cut value is .500					

Source: Primary Data.

Among the independent variables taken for the study, the contribution of each independent variable was observed in its significance statistically. The results showed that the nutritional, price, and price factors of similar food at nearby food joints had high odds ratios but were insignificant. Table 4 shows the logistic regression results of the seven considered independent variables, among which only two variables are statistically significant and influential and are indicated with * and ** in the Table 4.

The influence direction of the independent variables ‘sufficient quantity’ is positive. Thus the more the quantity of food, the more the positive impact on usage. Again the independent variable “discomfort” the influence is towards negative implying that the more the discomfort felt during usage, the less the need for further usage of the food meal scheme. This signifies that any change in the amount of food served or in how uncomfortable the changes are has a positive effect on the users' household costs. This outcomes shows that to increase the positive impact on household expenses of the users the policy direction should be aimed at the sufficient quantity of food served in the canteen.

Table 4: Showing Results of Logistics Regression

Variables	B	Standard Error	Sig.		Odds Ratio
Nutritious	0.890	0.585	0.136		2.435
Food Accompaniment	-0.554	0.626	0.376		0.575
Price	0.191	0.412	0.643		1.210
Food joint	0.015	0.396	0.970		1.015
Sufficient quantity	-1.237	0.646	0.055	*	0.290
Discomfort	2.438	0.597	0.000	**	11.455
Covid-19	0.647	0.354	0.068		01.910

Source: Primary Data

The odds ratio was used to examine how the changes in the identified independent variables will affect the direction of positive impact on household expenses among the users while all the other factors remain constant. If the odds ratio was higher than 1 (OR>1), that independent variable is more likely to create a positive impact on household expenses among the Indira canteen users. The higher the odds ratio, the higher the chance they will have a positive impact on the household expenses of the Indira Canteen users. Conversely, if the independent variable OR<1, that variable is said to be less likely to impact the household expenses of the Indira Canteen user. On examination of the odds ratios, it was found that “sufficient quantity” & “food accompaniment” have an OR<1 signifying that both these variables are less likely to have a positive impact on household expenses of which sufficient quantity was found significant in the model.

We conclude that the Indira Canteen users did not consider food nutrition, food accompaniment, the price at Indira canteen, nearness to other food joints and the Covid-19 situation for their repeated usage but the users of the Indira Canteen rather patronized it due to discomfort (OR=11.4555) and “discomfort” was a significant variable which impacts their household expenses. Our logistic regression analysis on factors influencing high usage of the canteen showed that high importance of “sufficient quantity” and “discomfort” was the strong-dependent predictor of usage. This has important guiding significance for how care for the less privileged urbanites are designed and implemented, as well as how to meet their needs for food security and household expenses. Based on the study, we wish to postulate that in order to drive the objective of the “zero hunger” policy matter, the authority should focus on parameters of “sufficient quantity”-in other words value for the money spent on food is derived by the users. The second factor “discomfort” indicates that the users are increasingly concerned about their quality of life- the degree of comfort of usage of Indira Canteen is becoming crucial factor influencing its further usage. The authorities in order to ensure the targeted segment of society does benefit from the implementation of the policy must consider not only menu but also on the customer value, quick service, and quantity in the scheme

The next research question.

- 3) Research Question 3-How is having a food security card or not having a food security card related to how often people use the canteen?

We argue that owning a food security card will influence usage of the Indira canteen. The public distribution system issued ration card holders has names of the members of their households, based upon which monthly rations of food rations are brought at subsidised rates from the identified public distribution centre. Any member whose name appears on the ration card can collect on behalf of the family if her or his biometric identification was captured on the point of sale machine at the distribution centre which collects the data through the internet. If the internet fails, the family member's radar card identification number was collected. Although there are many earlier studies examining the benefits of ration cards and their usage among the users, there exists a dearth of research examining how the ownership of the ration card influences the perspective and usage of public meal schemes of adults in an urban set-up. We argue that card ownership mediates the relationship between the frequency of meals taken and the user's perception that the Indira canteen helps household expense reduction. To put it differently, individuals who own a food security card are able to cope with food security on their own and do not use the Indira canteen. The reason why owning a food security card can mediate the relationship between usage of the canteen and the user's opinion that Indira Canteen helps reduce household expenses was that the food security card makes a positive contribution from an economic perspective to help an individual manage his household expenses efficiently. Using "ration cards," the user can purchase food grains and pulses at their local fair price shops at subsidised rates. This arrangement could deter him from using Indira Canteen. We thus formulate the hypothesis as-

HA₂-Owning a food security card mediates the usage of Indira Canteen and the user's view that Indira Canteen positively reduces household expenses.

A mediation analysis was conducted using Hayes process model 4, where the card's ownership was conceptualised to mediate the user's usage of the canteen and his opinion that the Indira canteen helps to reduce household expenses (Figure 1). Regression analysis was used to investigate the hypothesis. The exogenous variable is considered as the frequency of meals, and the endogenous variables in the model are owning a ration card and the belief that the canteen services reduce household expenses. The study looked at how having a ration card affects the relationship between how often people eat and how they think the canteen affects their household costs.

Figure 1: Mediation Model

The results revealed an insignificant indirect effect of the impact of meal intake frequency on the user’s perception ($b = 0.0804$, $t = 1.4823$), not supporting the null hypothesis. Furthermore, the direct effect of meal frequency on the user’s perception of household expense reduction in the presence of the mediator was also found insignificant ($b = 0.1098$, $p > .05$). A model of owning a ration card as a mediator in the relationship between frequent meal intake and a user’s positive impact on the household was not supported. The mediation analysis summary is presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Mediation Analysis Summary

Relationship	Total Effect	Direct Effect	Indirect Effect	Confidence Interval		T-Statistics	Conclusion
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Meal_Frequency->Own_Rationcard->Reduce_HH_Expense	0.0804	-0.0217	0.1021	-0.1314	0.3288	1.4823	Nil Mediation
	$p > .05$	$p > .05$					

Source: Primary Data

We conclude that usage of the ownership of a ration card (public distribution card) in the model was not significant as there was no evidence of mediation. Thus, patrons who own ration cards do not consider the ownership of the same pertinent to deciding whether to use or not use the Indira Canteen for a reduction in household expenses. A non-significant mediation model indicates that the association between the IV (frequency of having a meal) and the DV (perception of household expense reduction) was not reduced significantly by the inclusion of the mediator (owning a ration card). The role of the food security card in creating a feeling of security was limited to the geographic access of the card holders in the area of issue. To put it differently, until recently, the holder of a ration card could only procure subsidised food within the cardholder’s hometown. We have presently revealed that the food security card issued by the government of India does not support adults’ perception of food security.

We, thus, address the next research question.

- 4) Research Question 4: What elements of the patron’s usage of the Indira Canteen have a positive impact on his perception of the social good of the Indira Canteen?

A step-wise multiple regression analysis was performed. The hypothesis "Significance of positive impact with the usage of Indira Canteen" was validated. The independent variables(X n) considered are: good clean environment, quality food, tasty menu, healthy food, fibre, and fruit, while the dependent variable(Y) was the patron’s perception of the social good of the canteen. The results showed an R value of 0.786, which indicates the five subscale independent variables explain 78.6% of the change in the dependent variable(Y) and the model passed the F test (F = 78.880, p = 0.001). Table 6 shows a significant impact of predicting the perception of social good of the Indira Canteen based on the independent variables: good clean environment, quality food, tasty food, healthy food, and fibre and fruit.

Table 6: Summary of Step-Wise Regression Coefficients

Variables	β	Beta	P-Value	R	R ²	F Statistic	Durbin-Watson
Constant	3.924	-	(0.000) **	0.786	0.618	20.153	1.942
Good Clean(X1)	0.582	0.558	(0.000) **				
Quality Food(X2)	0.401	0.384	(0.000) **				
Tasty Menu(X3)	0.282	0.270	(0.000) **				
Health Food(X4)	0.244	0.234	(0.000) **				
Fibre & Fruit(X5)	0.186	0.178	(0.000) **				

Source: Computed from primary data. ** Significance @ 1 per cent level.

Dependent Variable- Social Good, * p<0.001.

Source: Primary Data

A significant regression equation was found (F (5,244) =20.153, p 0.001) with an R2 of 0.618. The predicted stepwise regression model of the social benefit of the Indira Canteen is as below

$$Y = 3.924 + 0.582 (X1) + 0.401 (X2) + 0.282 (X3) + 0.244 (X4) + 0.186 (X5) \quad [1]$$

The results suggest that good, clean infrastructure (X1) has a significant positive influence on Social Goodness(Y), while quality of food (X2) has the next best significant positive influence, followed by tasty (X3), healthy (X4), and fibre & fruits (X5)—reflecting that the state-run canteen has a higher probability of increasing the perception of social goodness among the Indira canteen users by maintaining a clean, good environment and providing quality food in the canteen on a regular basis. This finding is found to be in line with the recommendation of Paslakis et al. (2021), who emphasised that food security and healthy eating attitudes and behaviour today are the global priority given the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic as it ensures not only current but also future health and wellbeing of the citizens. This was further reinforced by the findings of Duncan and Claeys (2018), who conducted a study on food security governance, where they emphasised re-building sustainable and just food systems as important tools. The crucial factors of food accessibility and affordability among the common people are critical measures of food security. Any default in these two will severely impact the

citizens' positive view of the government's policy of meal accessibility, affordability, and utilization. We conclude that as a user's perception of the environment and quality has a lot of importance and, if left unchecked, can lead to low quality and unhealthy meals for the patrons. The social goodness perception of the Indira canteen users may not be high if ignored. As the number of patrons increases, there are chances of corruption in the supply chain of the scheme; it is a challenge to keep track at which point there could be disruptive corruption.

5. DISCUSSION

The International Council of Science (ICSU) launched a new initiative — "Future Earth" sees food security as a combination of three main components: utilisation, accessibility, and availability. The urban food supply chain requires resilience in its core structure to withstand turbulence in terms of climate vulnerability, disasters, and calamities. In addition to the turbulence, the mobility of the urban immigrant population further causes food insecurity. The key purpose of this research was to uncover pertinent questions about a food scheme launched in the urban city of Bengaluru and its role in coping with food security's three dimensions of accessibility, availability, and optimal utilisation and the demographic profiles of the users. The findings of this study are interpreted in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, which was a major disruptor for many governmental interventions. The economic and social lock-downs, coupled with unemployment, were a key stressor for the urban poor. Their lack of access to support ensuring food accessibility and food availability became the most important challenge for establishing a sustainable food security program. From this study, while profiling demographics of the users, we found that the younger population utilised the facility more than the average adult population. Likewise gender played a vital role—males scored higher frequency of usage. This agrees with the findings that female-headed households lack food security (Sekhampu, 2017; Bashir et al., 2012). Non-salaried people used the facility more than salaried people, while people with ration cards frequented it less frequently compared to people without ration cards. This reinforces earlier studies that showed that higher-income households are more food-secure in comparison to lower-income households (Gregory, Mancino & Coleman-Jensen, 2019). It was revealed that salaried people experience fewer adverse effects of food shortages while low-income households seek alternative choices to prevent starvation, and the Indira canteen has served this purpose. The users are increasingly concerned about their quality of life- the degree of comfort of usage of Indira Canteen along with the quantity of food served is the crucial factors influencing its further usage. Furthermore ownership of a ration card also have insignificant impact on the usage of the food canteen indicating that users are very concerned about household expense management. If the Government intends to have more patronage, then provide healthy, tasty food should be the focus of the PPP, additionally cleanliness and quality of food requirement the same if not more attention to encourage patronage.

6. CONCLUSION

People cannot be considered food secure until they believe they are and until there is consistency in food availability, accessibility, and proper utilization. The poor give careful consideration to their spending decisions because a significant portion of their income goes not only toward the purchase of food but also its consumption. The urban poor, in addition to food expenditure, have an additional challenge of living expenses. The ability of poor people to manage their basic needs in the absence of regular income was very low. The findings of this study highlight critical contextual and social factors that require primary attention, including strengthening government interventions in PPP initiatives and ensuring food quality in meal programmes. Unfortunately eating regimen quality is always associated with lower family pay (French, Tangney, Crane, Wang & Appelhans, 2019).

As hunger, malnutrition among the poor are another danger facing India, additional Government assistance through subsidised meal schemes such as Indira Canteen for working adults play an important role in providing relief to the poor. Hunger politics has a significant impact on the poor and their political alliance. Thus it becomes imperative for the legislators have options to work on quality assurance, monitoring measures, identify more PPP partners to widen the scope of the scheme state wide to address the three dimensions: accessibility, affordability, and utilization for mitigation of food insecurity.

Through this research, we have attempted to understand these dimensions in the meals programme launched by the Karnataka State Government in its capital city-Bengaluru. Through this research, we note that the Government of Karnataka, using the Indira Canteens in the metropolitan region, has played a significant and vital role in addressing the fundamental issues of SDG2-accessibility, affordability, and utilisation of food. According to Fanzo, Covic et al. (2020), food systems must improve supply chain infrastructure to make sure that nutritious foods are cheap, even for the poor. Confirming their view, the Indira Canteen, through its efficient supply chain model, is able to provide nutritious, cheap food for the urban poor in Bengaluru City.

7. LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

Despite the many positive contributions it makes, this paper has a few limitation that need to be addressed. First, the urban metropolitan population of India being 371.1 million (Census, 2011), Bengaluru's population being 8.5 million (Census, 2011), i.e., about 2.2 percent, the people in Bengaluru represent less than 3 percent of the total urban metropolitan population. The study was limited to three major wards in Bengaluru City from among the 198 wards. Major part of the study was conducted during the breakfast and lunch timings of the facilities. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic in Bengaluru City, the responses of the sampled respondents who patronage the facilities were taken for research.

8. FUTURE RESEARCH

There is no single solution to food security problems. Our study results show that the intended beneficiaries do utilise the food distribution canteen in spite of the food security card issue. Our study provides an important policy implication regarding the implementation of such schemes in the public distribution system. The findings of this study present a wealth of opportunities that the political authority at the government level, as well as stakeholders of the PPP and other interested parties, could investigate.

Future opportunities that Government of Karnataka may consider similar such interventions and implement them in governmental offices across the state in all major districts, thus enlarging the reach. Similar studies on Indira Canteen addressing further three dimensions of food security must be regularly carried out to identify problems, issues for interventional programs. Research on an unexplored area of food wastage in the public-distributed cooked meal supply chain is another focus opportunity.

The goals of the future study may be modified to understand profit maximisation of the PPP stakeholders and the satisfaction of intended beneficiaries. Because the portability of ration cards was not recognised in all Indian states, the state government must initiate social and strategic initiatives, primarily to address food security issues with assistance from the Centre. Studies on the stability of the canteen's operations can provide support and finance through their local budget the cost of the canteen's operations. Finally calling investors at the local level and ensuring supply and pricing stability can a feature of further study.

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- 1) Views and opinions expressed in this study are the views and opinions of the authors,
- 2) The NITI Aayog's or the National Institution for Transforming India- a policy think-tank and an advisory body of the Government of India- has released India's first multidimensional poverty index (MPI) in November 2021. It scores India as 0.118. In the Urban areas of India, the MPI scores is 0.08 while it reported 0.155 as the score in rural areas of India. Among the various states of India, Karnataka State MPI score is reported as 13.16. The 12 core indicators that make up India's first-ever national MPI measure are health and nutrition, education, and standard of living, including nutrition, child and adolescent mortality, prenatal care, years of schooling, school attendance, etc.

Declaration of Interest Statement:

The authors declare that they have no known competing interest-financial or personal that has influenced the work/research conducted in this article.

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